

Evaluation of Approximate Atomic Weights

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A semi-empirical equation correlating isotopic mass, its mass number, and atomic number has been made the basis for deriving relations that yield approximate values of atomic weights of 91 elements from helium to uranium from a mere knowledge of the atomic numbers of the elements.

The main nucleons, contributing towards nuclear mass, are the protons and the neutrons. As one examines the Periodic Table, the variations in the ratio of proton and neutron numbers in the nuclei of the elements become evident. It is therefore not very easy to comprehend the approximate atomic weight of an element, barring a few at the start, from a mere knowledge of the atomic number of the element.

Different investigators, such as Born and others, have sought to relate nuclear mass in terms of charge (proton number) and mass number of the nucleus. Consideration of some aspects of "liquid drop model" of nucleus together with other operating influences, e.g., coulombic force of interaction, led Weizsäcker (*Z. Physik*, 1935, 96, 431; vide also Engler and Green, *Phys. Rev.*, 1953, 91, 40) to suggest a semi-empirical equation for the mass of a nucleus, viz.,

$$M = m_p Z + m_n (A - Z) - \alpha A + \beta A^2 + \epsilon Z^2 A^{-1} + \gamma \left(Z - \frac{A}{2} \right)^2 / A + \delta \quad \dots (1)$$

where, m_p = mass of proton = 1.008, m_n = mass of neutron = 1.0086, A = mass number of the nucleus, Z = atomic number, and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \epsilon$ are constants; $\alpha = 15.04$ mamu, $\beta = 14.00$ mamu, $\gamma = 83$ mamu, $\epsilon = 0.627$ mamu, and $\delta = \pm \frac{0.035}{A^2}$ mamu or 0. This relation provides fair values of stable isotopic mass provided that A and Z are known. In the present communication, an endeavour has been made to obtain a simplified equation, independent of A terms, that can readily be utilised for approximate atomic weight calculation.

For the stablest nucleus of a given mass number, A , the atomic number Z_A is given by

$$Z_A = \frac{m_n - m_p + \gamma}{2\epsilon A^{-1} + 2\gamma A^{-1}}$$

or

$$A = 1.986 Z_A \left[\frac{\epsilon}{\gamma} A^i + 1 \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

Most of the elements up to uranium ($Z=92$) exist in isotopic forms with different values of A . To apply equation (2) to these isotopes of different elements, one reasonable assumption is made that for any particular Z -value, the theoretically stablest nucleus, governed by equation (2), corresponds to one or the other of the naturally occurring isotopes. For elements with no isotope, the existing species represents the stablest entity.

Although minimum potential energy is the main criterion for indexing the stablest isotope corresponding to a given Z , other physical properties, such as packing fraction values and relative percentage abundance, it may be pointed out, are also qualitative indicators of the degree of stability. Judging from the stand-points of packing fraction and relative abundance, isotopes with greatest percentage abundance do not appear to have always maximum negative packing fraction values. All the same, if for an element, the mass numbers of such isotopes are considered which contribute most towards and make up together at least 90% of the abundance of the element, this group will assuredly contain the stablest species; an average mass number value A (hypothetical) may then be calculated for this group. The relation (2) will not apply to this average mass

number A . It is assumed that a modified form of equation (2), viz.,

$$A = 1.986 Z \left[\frac{\epsilon}{\gamma} A^{\frac{1}{3}} + 1 \right] + \lambda \quad \dots (2a)$$

will apply to the hypothetical average mass number calculated for each element. The deviation expected of A , not representing the mass number of the stablest species, is covered by the term λ , the form of which will be ascertained later. It will be seen afterwards that λ actually possesses two sets of values dependent on Z , the first holding good from helium to zinc and the second, from zinc to uranium. In the above equation, Z_A is deprived of its subscript and replaced by Z for, firstly, all the isotopes of a particular element, whether the stablest or not, have equal proton number and secondly, the additional indication that A in equation (2a) does not represent necessarily the mass number of the stablest isotope.

Hubbard and Meggers ("Periodic Chart of the Atoms", Table IV, p. 31) have compiled a list of stable and longest-lived isotopes of non-radioactive and radioactive elements with their relative percentage occurrence in nature. The

FIG. 1

data supplied by them have been utilised in evaluating average A and hence of $A^{\frac{1}{3}}$ of elements from He ($Z = 2$) to U ($Z = 92$). A plot of these average $A^{\frac{1}{3}}$ values against corresponding atomic numbers (Z) yields points which fall roughly on two straight lines (Fig. 1) represented by the equations:

$$A^{\frac{1}{3}} = m_1 Z + c_1 \quad \dots (3a)$$

and

$$A^{\frac{1}{3}} = m_2 Z + c_2 \quad \dots (3b)$$

where, $m_1 = 0.487$, $c_1 = 2.2$, and $m_2 = 0.347$, $c_2 = 6.5$.

One characteristic feature noted in respect of the two straight lines is that elements lying on the decreasing portion and a little beyond of the well-known packing fraction curve lie on the line defined by (3a), i.e., from He to Zn, but those beyond zinc, which lie on the upward rising part of the curve, are governed by equation (3b). The two straight lines intersect on the ordinate corresponding to the abscissa value $Z = 30$.

Now, from (1), omitting δ , which is small, and introducing the values of m_n , α , and A (given by 2a) we have

$$M = \left(1.97 \frac{\epsilon}{\gamma} Z + \beta \right) A^{\frac{1}{3}} + \epsilon Z^2 A^{-\frac{1}{3}} + \gamma \left(Z - \frac{A}{2} \right)^2 / A + 1.969 Z + 0.993 \lambda \quad \dots (4)$$

I. For elements up to $Z = 30$, $\gamma \left(Z - \frac{A}{2} \right)^2 / A$ is very small and can be neglected. The values of $A^{-\frac{1}{3}}$ for these elements, viz., helium to zinc, vary between the limits 0.629 and 0.248 over an atomic number change of 28 units. These considerations together with (3a) convert (4) into

$$M \approx (0.0147Z + 0.014) (0.487Z + 2.2) + \epsilon Z^2 \left\{ 0.629 + \frac{1}{28} (2 - Z) (0.629 - 0.248) \right\} \\ + 1.969 Z + 0.993 \lambda$$

or $M = 2.008Z + 7.57 \times 10^{-3} Z^2 - 8.5 \times 10^{-6} Z^3 + 0.031 + 0.993 \lambda \quad \dots (5)$

The representation of A^{-1} by $(0.656 - 0.0136Z)$ above should not be construed to define a linear dependence of the former on Z . This approximate expression, derivable from actual values, is, in reality, equivalent to $(1.656 - e^{0.0136Z})$, where higher powers of Z , variable from 2 to 30, are reasonably neglected in the exponential expansion. It is seen that a plot of $(1.55 - e^{0.0136Z})$ against Z produces a curve, which closely retraces the one obtained by plotting actual A^{-1} values against Z . Since there is hardly any difference of 0.1 between the two expressions, the approximate representation of A^{-1} by $(0.656 - 0.0136Z)$ is justified.

The utilisation of the foregoing equation depends on finding out a suitable value for λ . An indirect method of obtaining approximate equivalent to λ consists in comparing the differences between actual atomic weights of a few elements, selected at random (say $Z = 10, 17,$ and 30), and those given by $(M - 0.993 \lambda)$, deducible from equation (5). The differences, equal to -0.993λ , can mostly, within a few tenths of 1 amu, be represented by the expression $0.05 \times (Z - Z_{\text{He}})$, Z_{He} being the atomic number of helium, the initial element belonging to curve (1) of Fig. 1. With this value of 0.993λ introduced, equation (5) is converted to

$$M = 1.95Z + 7.57 \times 10^{-3} Z^2 - 8.5 \times 10^{-6} Z^3 + 0.131 \quad \dots (6)$$

In deducing equation (6), average mass number A of the elements, existing in different isotopic forms, was considered. Hence M may be taken to represent the atomic weight of the elements. Equation (6) is valid, for reasons already stated, for elements inclusive of and lying between helium and zinc.

11. For Elements lying between and inclusive of Zn and U

The terms $\epsilon Z^2 A^{-1}$ and $\gamma \left(Z - \frac{A}{2} \right)^2 / A$ occurring in equation (4) vary from element to element. It will be attempted to replace these, in an effort at simplification, by terms independent of A , that on the average will give more or less correct values for these terms.

The value of A^{-1} varies from 0.248 for Zn to 0.161 for U. The difference of 0.087 is thus spread over a range of 62 atomic number units ($Z_{\text{U}} = 92$ and $Z_{\text{Zn}} = 30$). The approximate substitute for the term $\epsilon Z^2 A^{-1}$ will therefore be $\epsilon Z^2 \{ 0.248 + (30 - Z) \times 0.0014 \}$.

Similar considerations, when applied to $\gamma \left(Z - \frac{A}{2} \right)^2 / A$, yield the term $\gamma [0.0961 + (Z - 30) \times 0.0478]$ as an approximate equivalent for the latter. These equivalents together with equation (3b) change equation (4) into

$$M = 2.073Z + 5.28 \times 10^{-3} Z^2 - 8.8 \times 10^{-7} Z^3 - 0.02 + 0.993 \lambda \quad \dots (7)$$

It may incidentally be noted that $(0.29 - 0.0014Z)$, the assumed equivalence of A^{-1} , is what an expansion of $(1.29 - e^{0.0014Z})$ would lead to after proper neglect of small terms for Z values ranging from 30 to 92. The expression $(1.29 - e^{0.0014Z})$ yields values close to the ones actually obtained for A^{-1} for any particular Z . The value of 0.993λ in equation (7) can be expressed by a similar term as before, viz., $0.05 \times (Z - Z_{\text{He}})$, where Z_{He} is the atomic number of initial element on the second straight line of Fig. 1. With $0.993 \lambda = 0.05Z - 1.5$, equation (7) yields

$$M = 2.12Z + 5.28 \times 10^{-3} Z^2 - 8.8 \times 10^{-7} Z^3 - 1.52 \quad \dots (8)$$

This equation may be utilised in computing the atomic weights of elements with atomic numbers lying between $Z = 30$ and $Z = 92$, *i.e.*, from zinc to uranium.

Before examining the applicability of equations (6) and (8) to different elements, it will be worthwhile to consider the conditions under which these were derived.

- (1) The use of an average A value for an element, though it may not have any physical significance.
- (2) Equation (2), when modified by introduction of an additional term λ , applies to these average A values.
- (3) Substitution of terms A^{-1} and $\left(Z - \frac{A}{2}\right)^2 / A$ by average terms involving Z only.

Working within the framework of these limitations, the expected results by the application of equations (6) and (8) should only be approximate. Nevertheless, it is interesting to examine the extent of accuracy when the two equations are appropriately applied over the entire range of 91 elements. The following table summarises the results.

TABLE I

Range of accuracy.	Atomic numbers of the elements.	Total.
Within 1 amu of real atomic weight	2 to 15, 17, 19, 21, 24, 26, 27, 29 to 33, 35, 37 to 40, 42 to 44, 46, 48, 49, 59 to 63, 65, 67 to 78, 87, 88, 90, 92.	61
Within 2 amu of real atomic weight	16, 20, 22, 23, 25, 28, 36, 41, 45, 47, 50, 51, 53, 55, 58, 64, 66, 79, 83, 89.	20
Within 3 amu of real atomic weight	18, 34, 57, 86, 54.	5
Beyond 3 amu of real atomic weight	52, 56, 84, 85, 91.	5

A glance at the table will reveal that barring five elements, the atomic weights of 86 elements can roughly be estimated by either equation (6) or (8). Of these, for as many as 61 elements the values lie within 1 unit of real atomic weight, and for 20 elements, within 2 units. The values afforded by these equations are too approximate to be of any practical utility. Nevertheless, it is seen that atomic weights can be expressed, with a fair measure of accuracy, as a function of atomic number only.

The cases of appreciable deviations (two bottom columns of Table I, where error exceeds 2 amu) are mostly covered by the following categories :

- (1) The so-called misfits in the Periodic Table, *viz.*, A, Te, Pa.
- (2) The rare gas members, *viz.*, A, Xe, Rn (of these argon comes under category 1 also).
- (3) The sulphur analogues, *viz.*, Se, Te, Po (of these Te also appears in 1).

Three stray elements, vanadium, barium, and lanthanum, fall outside the categories and yet exhibit deviations exceeding 2 amu.

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